

INDUSTRIAL PROCESSING OF LITHIUM-ION BATTERIES

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Abstract. *In recent years, the consumption of lithium-based materials has increased several-fold due to the growing demand for lithium batteries worldwide. The lithium-ion battery market is growing steadily every year, and by 2024, the market size will reach the equivalent of US\$54 billion. Currently, lithium metal is extracted from natural minerals, but this process requires a lot of energy. Moreover, lithium consumption increased by 18% from 2018 to 2019, and given the limited lithium reserves, it can be assumed that lithium depletion will be inevitable. This has led to the development of lithium recycling technologies from lithium-ion batteries. This paper discusses technologies that can recycle lithium compounds from spent lithium-ion batteries according to individual stages and methods. The stages are divided into pre-treatment and lithium extraction stages. The latter is divided into three main methods: pyrometallurgy, hydrometallurgy, and electrochemical separation. The processes, advantages, disadvantages, lithium recovery efficiency, cost, environmental pollution, and commercialization level of each method are compared and quantitatively analyzed. Despite the growing attention and development of various lithium recycling technologies, less than 1 percent of lithium is currently recycled. We hope that this paper will contribute to the improvement of lithium waste recycling technology and stimulate further interest and development in the field of lithium recycling.*

Keywords: *lithium, pyrometallurgy, hydrometallurgy, electrochemical separation, recycling, lithium-ion, energy.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that at present time the discussions about lithium-based technologies have become the mainstream of energy research. Since its first commercial introduction in 1991, lithium-ion battery has become one of the main energy technologies and has been continuously researched for several decades to develop the future energy market. However, lithium is unevenly distributed throughout the world and is a limited element. In addition, with the rapid development of electric vehicle (EV) and energy storage system (ESS) technologies, the demand for lithium is rapidly increasing. Lithium consumption has more than doubled in the past decade. For these reasons, the importance of lithium recycling has become increasingly clear. This article describes the current status of lithium and highlights the importance of lithium recycling. In addition, the article describes the various methods used to recycle lithium, as well as the process,

advantages, and disadvantages of each method, and provides recommendations for research and development in lithium recycling technology. In 2011, 30% of lithium consumption was in ceramics and glass, followed by batteries and lubricants/castings.

However, the use of batteries in small electronic devices such as smartphones and laptops, as well as larger systems such as electric vehicles (EVs) and energy storage systems (ESSs), has resulted in 60% of lithium consumption being in batteries. Lithium is chosen as a battery material for three reasons: it is the lightest metal, it has the highest electrochemical potential of all metals, and it has the highest energy density of all metals. In addition, lithium is used in batteries, as well as in ceramics, glass, and lubricants/castings with special chemistry. The addition of lithium to ceramics increases the melting rate of glass, lowers its viscosity, and reduces its melting point. In addition, lithium's high coefficient of thermal expansion makes ceramics resistant to thermal shock and increases their mechanical strength.

Definitely, lithium is produced from natural resources. Although lithium is widely available, its reserves and production are unevenly distributed around the world. South American countries such as Chile, Bolivia, and Argentina contain more than 70% of the world's lithium reserves. Australia produces the most lithium (43.5% of the world's production), followed by Chile (32.8%). Argentina and China export the most lithium.

It is known to everyone that lithium is mined from two natural sources: ores and salt pans. Lithium can be extracted from spodumene, petalite, and eucryptite, and the lithium content of these ores ranges from 2% to 5.5%. The minerals are crushed, separated by gravity flotation, concentrated, and heat treated to produce a lithium solution, followed by water washing, acidification, and pressure washing.[1]

The second method of extracting lithium is from salt pans or brines. Lithium-rich brines are mainly found in Argentina, Bolivia, Chile, China and the United States. The lithium content and the magnesium to lithium ratio in the brine are important factors affecting the cost and time of production. The lithium content of brines currently used in production ranges from 0.02 to 5%. Lithium is extracted from salt water by precipitation. The sun evaporates the brine water in a pond, then precipitates NaCl and KCl as well as the lithium concentration in the solution, then Ca(OH)_2 is added to the concentrated lithium brine to remove Mg and sulfate by precipitation. The remaining Ca and Na_2CO_3 in the concentrate are removed by precipitation using CaCO_3 . This liquid is then filtered, washed and heated to 80-90 °C to react with Na_2CO_3 to form Li_2CO_3 .

Although extracting lithium from ore provides a higher concentration of lithium, it is a more energy-intensive process, which makes the production cost slightly higher than extracting from brine. Thus, 87% of lithium is produced by processing brine.

Demand for lithium processing. If it can be considered the prices of lithium on the world market by year, then, firstly, in 2016-2017, the price of lithium was estimated at 5,000-10,000 US dollars. However, by 2021-2022, due to a sharp increase in demand for lithium, the price of 1 ton of lithium on the world market reached an average of 80,000 US dollars. Since then, large companies around the world have focused on mining and processing, driven by the need for lithium. Meanwhile the market price of 1 ton of lithium is 40,000 dollars. It means that there is still a high demand for lithium from manufacturing companies today, as well as the need to improve lithium extraction and recycling technologies. The shift to clean energy has led to a steady increase in the use of personal electronics, electric vehicles (EVs), and ESSs powered by lithium batteries. These trends have led to the expansion of the lithium-ion battery market to \$44 billion

in 2020. The growth of the ESS and EV battery markets has further accelerated this expansion. To illustrate the potential growth in demand, it is worth noting that smartphones, laptops, and tablets contain approximately 2 g, 6 g, and 20 g of lithium per device, respectively, while an EV battery requires about 20 kg of lithium, which is equal to 1,000 more than a smartphone, and a 10 MWh ESS requires at least 700 kg of lithium. Rising lithium-ion battery prices could weaken the lithium-ion battery market.

Certainly, lithium consumption increased by 18% from 49,100 tonnes in 2018 to 57,700 tonnes in 2019. Global lithium reserves are estimated to be approximately 17 billion tonnes. It has been estimated that if annual consumption growth of 18% continues, global lithium reserves will be exhausted in the near future. In 30 years, lithium demand will be approximately 63 million tonnes, exceeding remaining reserves by 40 million tonnes. Although additional lithium reserves may eventually be discovered, demand growth is expected to accelerate due to the expanding lithium-ion battery market.

Research methods and objects.

Regarding the waste lithium-ion batteries, research in lithium recycling has focused primarily on waste lithium-ion batteries. Lithium-ion batteries operate through the movement of lithium ions and electrons and consist of an anode, cathode, electrolyte, and separator. The cathode and anode are bonded to aluminum or copper foil with a polymer binder such as polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) to provide electrical conductivity and stability. Electrolytes are usually liquids and carry lithium ions between the cathode and anode. These are typically lithium salts (such as LiPF₆) dissolved in organic solvents such as ethylene carbonate (EC) or dimethyl carbonate (DMC). Polymers such as polypropylene (PP) or polyethylene (PE) are used as separators to prevent physical contact and direct electron transfer between the cathode and anode.

Besides that, a lithium-ion battery can last up to three years in a small electronic device and five to ten years in a larger device; given that nickel-cadmium batteries last fifteen to twenty years and lead-acid batteries last five to ten years, this is less than the lifespan of other batteries. Currently, 80% of lithium-ion batteries are used in small electronics. Electric vehicles with electric drive account for less than 20%. In 2012, the volume of lithium-ion battery recycling was estimated at 700 tons. This value is gradually increasing every year and have reach 250,000 tons by 2020.

With the widespread adoption of EVs and ESTs, the amount of lithium-ion batteries in use is expected to increase. Waste lithium-ion batteries are collected by government agencies or companies authorized by the manufacturer. Consumers typically dispose of lithium-ion batteries at designated landfills or collect them directly from the relevant authorities. However, only 2-5% of lithium-ion batteries are collected in Australia, the European Union, and the United States. Low collection rates are due to a lack of consumer awareness and a tendency to resell electronics rather than recycle them. Although the situation may vary by country, the legal and physical infrastructure for large-scale collection and efficient, safe, and cost-effective transportation of recycled lithium-ion batteries is lacking. Significant improvements are needed to significantly increase the collection rate. Lithium can be extracted from a lithium-ion battery in two main ways. Since lithium is difficult to separate from the packaged battery, the recycled battery undergoes a pre-treatment process to separate the lithium-containing active material (cathode, anode) from the peripheral parts (plastic, polymer). Then, lithium is chemically separated from the active materials using pyrometallurgical, hydrometallurgical and electrochemical extraction methods. Two processes are explained: pre-treatment and lithium extraction.

It is true that pre-treatment methods for waste lithium-ion batteries make it difficult to determine the residual capacity of the waste lithium-ion battery. Even after the battery is discharged, some charge may remain in it. In addition, since lithium-ion batteries contain various materials, direct recycling of batteries is ineffective. This is why the pre-cutting process is important. Used lithium-ion batteries can only be safely separated into parts after they are completely discharged. Otherwise, the battery may explode or release toxic gases due to local short circuit.

Research results and analysis.

Definitely, different methods are used to extract lithium from the active material obtained from pretreatment. Most of the methods are aimed at extracting Co, Ni or Mn. This study focuses on lithium mining. In addition, methods that produce washing solutions are not included in this review. Figure 1 shows three lithium extraction methods: pyrometallurgy, hydrometallurgy and electrowinning.

Pyrometallurgy Pyrometallurgy uses high temperatures to remove organic matter by evaporation and causes reactions at the cathode and anode that make lithium water-soluble. Lithium was then recycled from the aqueous solution. The pretreated active ingredients were crushed and calcined. At temperatures above 700 °C, the lithium oxide of the metal cathode and anode reacts to form Li^2CO^3 and metal oxides. The reactions are shown in equations (1)-(5).

Then the calcined powder was washed with water to dissolve lithium (Li^2CO^3) in water. Metal oxides are insoluble in water. After washing by water filtration, the undissolved metal oxide and aqueous solution were separated to form Li^2CO^3 solution, and then the water was evaporated to obtain Li^2CO^3 (Figure 1). This method can recycle large volumes of recycled lithium-ion batteries. Lithium is extracted from pre-treated lithium-ion battery by pyrometallurgy using Li^2CO^3 and graphite.[2] The separated active materials were calcined in nitrogen at 1000 °C for 30 min to produce Co, Li^2CO^3 and graphite compounds. This compound was dissolved in water to separate lithium using wet magnetic separation. By separating lithium-ion batteries and calcining them at 800 °C for 45 minutes, they create a lithium-containing powder that is 50 times more soluble in water than the powder itself. This produces Li_2CO_3 , and LiF is mixed with the extraction solution. The cathode material is separated from the battery and calcined at 700 °C in a vacuum for 30 minutes. The calcined powder is converted to metal oxide Li^2CO^3 .

Some pyrometallurgy processes use additional acids in the roasting process to improve the efficiency of lithium recycling. Nitric acid is effectively used to nitrate lithium-ion battery scrap by burning it at 250°C for 60 minutes. After calcination, the lithium solution is obtained by washing with water.

Hydrometallurgy is the most common method for lithium extraction.[3] It ionizes lithium in active materials pre-treated with acids and bases, and then forms lithium solutions from which lithium can be extracted. Inorganic acids such as sulfuric acid, hydrochloric acid, and nitric acid are used in these processes. Among the redox agents, H_2O_2 is the most common reducing agent due to its low cost and non-toxicity. H_2O_2 can increase the rate of leaching reaction due to its

strong reducing ability. However, using a low pH acid can result in the release of harmful gases such as Cl^2 and NO^2 , which have a negative impact on the environment. Trials are also underway to use weaker acids such as oxalic or citric acid. [4] Lithium compounds can be created by leaching with acids or bases followed by precipitation, solvent extraction, or selective adsorption is then reacted with water (25 g/L).

Pyrometallurgy

Hydrometallurgy

Figure 2. General scheme of lithium recycling from pre-processed spent LIB components by hydrometallurgy.

It should be mentioned that recycling of lithium batteries is a global issue and many countries and companies are making significant efforts to find a solution. This process is not only

environmentally friendly but also economically beneficial. These efforts will make lithium a more environmentally friendly and cost-effective technology for future technologies by creating a natural recycling cycle similar to that of other elements. In addition to developing lithium recycling technologies, it is important to raise global awareness of lithium shortage and improve the perspectives of traders, developers and recyclers on this issue. In addition, political interest and government support are critical for a sustainable lithium economy.

Conclusion. By summerising it should be suggested that recycling of lithium-ion batteries not only contributes to a cleaner environment, but also has economic and technological significance. However, to improve the efficiency of this process, it is necessary to implement scientific and technical research and innovative technologies. Improving the recycling process will make battery production and disposal more efficient and play an important role in protecting the environment.

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